

The Influence of Digital Marketing Through SEO and Social Media Marketing Activities on Brand Awareness in Building Brand Equity and Brand Loyalty Site Pikiran-Rakyat.Com

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ABSTRACT: The massive development of the internet has triggered changes in all aspects and industries. Including the mass media industry, so that there is an era of convergence towards conventional media to survive in the digital era. Including the Harian Umum Pikiran Rakyat which has the online news site Pikiran-Rakyat.com in the shadow of Pikiran Rakyat Media Network. Pikiran-Rakyat.com is one of the brave media that provides a lot of information and news not only for the people of Greater Bandung or West Java. It can also be accessed nationally, like other competitors, namely Kompas and Tribun News. The aim of this research is: The aims to be obtained in this research which are designed and adapted to the problem formulation are as follows: Knowing the influence of using Search Engine Optimization on increasing brand awareness, Knowing the influence of Social Media Marketing Activities (SMMAs) on increasing brand awareness, Knowing the influence increasing brand awareness of brand equity and knowing the effect of increasing brand awareness on brand loyalty from Pikiran-Rakyat.com This research method is quantitative with descriptive analysis techniques and structural equation models or what are called Structural Equation Models (SEM) and Partial Last Square (PLS). The results of this research show that respondents' responses regarding Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Brand Awareness, Brand Equity and Brand Loyalty are in the good category, while responses to the Social Media Marketing Activities (SMMAs) variable are in the quite good category. The relationship between Search Engine Optimization (SEO) and Social Media Marketing Activities (SMMAs) has a positive effect on Brand Awareness. Meanwhile, the Brand Awareness relationship has a positive influence on both Brand Equity and Brand Loyalty.

KEYWORDS: Brand Equity, Brand Awareness, Brand Loyalty, Digital Marketing, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Social Media Marketing Activities (SMMAs).

INTRODUCTION

The development of the internet plays an important role in accelerating the dissemination of information. In the past, information was always obtained conventionally through print media such as newspapers, tabloids, and magazines. Information is also obtained through electronic media such as radio and television. Currently, the internet is present as a new media or new media in accelerating the dissemination of information to users around the world, especially in Indonesia. New media is a product of digital communication technology for mass media where it can be accessed through various digital devices, both computers and smartphones. According to data from the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) on the Indonesiabaik. id website, internet users in Indonesia reached 215.63 million people in the 2022-2023 period. This number increased by 2.67% compared to the previous period, which was 210.03 million users. The number of internet users is equivalent to 78.19% of Indonesia's total population of 275.77 million people. The large number of internet users in Indonesia is also seen from the duration of the longest internet use in various countries. Indonesia is the country with the longest internet usage in the world in 2022. Based on the data.ai report published on the dataindonesia. id website entitled The State of Mobile 2023, the duration of internet use in Indonesia was 5.7 hours per day in 2022. The duration of internet use in Indonesia increased by 5.56% compared to the previous year. In 2021, the average Indonesian population used the internet for 5.4 hours per day. Indonesia's position is followed by Singapore, Saudi Arabia, and Brazil. The average duration of internet usage in the three countries was monitored at 5.3 hours per day last year. Internet usage has now become a habit for Indonesian people from various circles. Both young and old often access the internet to support various activities. One of them is looking for news or information available from various sources, both hard news such as politics, law, social, international. Or soft news such as entertainment, tourism, culinary, to interesting tips that are useful for readers. Mass media portals compete to

create articles that are both trending (content that is the latest trend) and evergreen (content that is timeless). A survey from the Reuters Institute showed that in 2021, 89% of Indonesians relied on online media as their main source of news, followed by social media (64%) and television (58%). Only 20% of respondents accessed news through print media. This data reflects the technological disruption that encourages people to prefer online and social media over traditional media such as newspapers and magazines. Many conventional media in Indonesia have switched to the internet or stopped publishing print media. Mass media, such as the Pikiran Rakyat newspaper from West Java, invested in media convergence by launching the Pikiran-rakyat.com news site since 1996. This site allows access to information not only for the people of West Java, but also nationally, reaching internet users throughout Indonesia. In April 2023, Pikiran-Rakyat.com was ranked 4th in terms of the number of visits to news sites in Indonesia, according to Similarweb, after detik.com, kompas.com, and Tribunnews.com. To attract readers, Pikiran-Rakyat.com relies on organic content, which is content published at no cost. This content is part of organic marketing, which focuses on attracting customers naturally without paid advertising. This strategy includes increasing customer interaction through social media, website optimization, and creative content creation and is useful in finding prospects and increasing conversions. Organic content includes trending articles, quickly attracting readers' attention through social media platforms and websites. In addition, there is evergreen content that remains relevant for a long time. According to Redcomm Indonesia, online media such as Pikiran-Rakyat.com focus on creating interesting articles with keywords that are easy to search for and in accordance with Search Engine Optimization (SEO). The news presented is not only hard news, but also covers topics such as sports, including live streaming and match score predictions, especially those involving favorite teams such as Persib Bandung and other major events. Data from Similarweb shows that Pikiran-Rakyat.com competed closely with Suara.com in organic content between June and August 2023, excelling in searches related to sports events with the keyword "score 808," but losing in searches for "Timnas." Trending content, such as Twibbon, also attracted attention. To optimize digitalization, Pikiran Rakyat conducted digital marketing, especially through Search Engine Optimization (SEO), which increased the quantity and quality of traffic. SEO is also popular in digital marketing, ranking third after social media marketing and content marketing. In addition to SEO, Pikiran-Rakyat.com utilizes social media for promotion, with Twitter being the top platform based on traffic visits. Instagram accounts are also used to direct readers to the official website for complete information. Digital marketing activities, including Search Engine Optimization (SEO) and Social Media Marketing Activities (SMMAs), play an important role in increasing brand awareness, brand equity, and brand loyalty, as discussed in research by Krishnaprabha and Tarunika (2020). Pikiran-Rakyat.com, as a national online news portal, faces challenges in competition and unstable brand awareness, even though it is supported by organic content such as sports news and trending content. In addition, Pikiran-Rakyat.com operates through collaboration with partner news portals in various regions, so if the partner portal experiences an increase in traffic, Pikiran-Rakyat.com also benefits from its traffic. Pikiran-Rakyat.com needs to increase brand awareness, brand equity, and brand loyalty through collaboration with clients to advertise in the form of advertorials. This shows the need to strengthen digital marketing, including the use of SEO and social media marketing activities (SMMAs). The social media team, which has been developed since December 2022, focuses on creating interesting content to increase visits and interactions with the audience. Digital marketing activities are expected to increase brand awareness, brand equity, and brand loyalty for Pikiran-Rakyat.com. Through digital marketing and presence on various social media platforms, Pikiran Rakyat, as an online news portal, shows its existence amidst the challenges of digitalization and disruption to conventional media.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Digital Marketing

Define digital marketing is any form of product or service marketing activity carried out virtually using digital media/internet (Agung, 2021).

B. Search Engine Optimization

Define search engine optimization is a process of improving the structure of a website and promoting it to appear in search engines, increasing its ranking and the number of visitors.(Antonius 2921)

C. Social Media Marketing Activities (SMMAs)

Social Media Marketing Activities according to research by Malarvizhi et al. (2022) is defined as the use of social media platforms and tools to promote products or services, engage with customers, and build brand awareness and loyalty. There are five components in social media marketing activities as follows:

1.) Entertainment (ENT):

Entertainment is the use of social media to provide entertaining content for users.

2.) Interactivity (INT):

An interactive feature that allows users to engage with the brand.

3.) Trendiness (TRE):

The use of social media to showcase the latest trends and innovations in the industry.

4.) Customization (CUS):

Customizing content and offerings to each user's preferences.

5.) Electronic word-of-mouth (EWOM):

The use of social media to share positive or negative experiences with a brand, which can influence the perceptions and behaviors of others.

D. Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is the ability of consumers to recognize and identify a brand in their minds. According to Wardana (2022), brand awareness is consumer awareness of the existence of a brand in its product class that distinguishes it from competing product brands in the same product class so that the brand can be recognized and remembered well in the minds of consumers.

E. Brand Equity

According to research from Malarvizhi et al. (2022), brand equity refers to the value and strength of a brand in the market. It represents the intangible assets and reputation of a brand, which can influence consumer perception, preference and behavior. Brand value is built through many factors such as brand awareness, brand image, brand loyalty, and perceived quality. The concept of brand equity is important in marketing because it can contribute to a brand's competitive advantage, customer loyalty, and financial performance.

F. Brand Loyalty

According to research by S. Krishnaprabha (2020), brand loyalty is the tendency of consumers to choose and buy certain products or brands consistently and continuously over a long period of time, even when there are other product or brand options available on the market.

Figure 1. Research Framework

HYPOTHESIS

H1 Search Engine Optimization (SEO) has a positive influence on brand awareness.

H2 Social Media Marketing Activities component: Entertainment has a positive relationship with brand awareness.

H3 Social Media Marketing Activities component: Interactivity has a positive relationship with brand awareness.

H4 Social Media Marketing Activities component: Trendiness has a positive relationship with brand awareness.

H5 Social Media Marketing Activities component: Customization has a positive relationship with brand awareness.

H6 Social Media Marketing Activities component: Electronic word-of-mouth (E-WOM) has a positive relationship with brand awareness.

H7 Brand Awareness has a positive relationship with Brand Equity.

H8 Brand Awareness has a positive relationship with Brand Loyalty.

METHODS

This study uses a quantitative method using descriptive research according to Indrawati (2015), which aims to identify factors or variables to measure an object but does not yet recognize the relationship between factors and variables. According to Surjaweni (2015:49), descriptive research is a study conducted with the main objective of providing an objective description of a situation. This study has 3 types of variables, namely independent variables, intermediate variables, and dependent variables. Independent variables are variables that are the cause or have theoretical possibilities that have an impact on other variables. The independent variables in this study are Search Engine Optimization (SEO) and Social Media Marketing Activities (SMMA).

The intermediate variable is a variable that is an intermediary between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The intermediate variable in this study is brand awareness. While the dependent variable is a variable that is influenced by other variables, and becomes the final variable of the study. The dependent variable in this study is brand equity and brand loyalty. The measurement scale used in this study is the Likert scale. In this study, the object used as the population is the readers of the Pikiran-rakyat.com site based on visitor traffic of 142.5 million, and the sample selected for this study was 100 respondents. The sampling technique used in this study is convenience sampling by selecting several members of the population as samples in order to obtain the information needed in this study. In this validity test, this study uses the correlation coefficient between variables to measure the convergence value. Guilford (1956) in Indrawati (2015) shows that the recommended minimum coefficient is 0.4. In the reliability test, according to Indrawati (2015), the most common measurement reliability is calculated using the Alpha-Cronbach Technique, requiring a minimum value of 0.7 for the measurement to be considered reliable. In the data analysis technique, the study has two or more dependent and independent variables using the structural equation model (SEM). The statistical analysis used in VB-SEM is the partial least squares (PLS) method, which aims to make predictions and discoveries (Indrawati, 2015). This study uses PLS statistical analysis because it has more than two dependent and independent variables. Partial Least Square (PLS), according to Abdillah and Jogiyanto (2015), is a multivariate statistical analysis technique using a comparison of multiple dependent variables with multiple independent variables. PLS is one of the SEM statistical methods based on variants designed for solving specific problems in data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Primary data is used by the researcher, the data collection comes from valid questionnaires totaling 100/400 respondents. Respondent Characteristics based on Gender, Age, Occupation and Average Income of internet users and visitors of Pikiran-Rakyat.com as the object of the study.

A. Measurement (Outer Model)

A measurement model is one that connects latent variables (indirect) with manifest variables (direct). Convergent validity is a validity that is proven if the scores obtained by the instrument that measures the concept, or measures the concept with different methods, have a high correlation. The correlation between the indicator score and the variable score is a measurement of the convergent validity of the measurement model. It is said that the indicator is valid if the AVE value is greater than 0.5. This means that the measurement met the convergent validity criteria (Indrawati, 2017: 69). The following are the test results using Smart PLS software:

Table 1. Convergent Validity

Variable	AVE	Critical Value	Model Evaluation
Search Engine Optimization (X ₁)	0,625	> 0,5	Valid
Social Media Marketing Activities (X ₂)	0,511		Valid
Brand Awareness (Z)	0,806		Valid
Brand Equity (Y ₁)	0,673		Valid
Brand Loyalty (Y ₂)	0,696		Valid

Table 1 shows that the three variables have AVE values that are greater than the critical value of 0.5. Thus, it can be concluded that all variables have met the requirements of convergent validity. Meanwhile, discriminant validity can be seen through the measurement of cross-loading factors by comparing AVE and correlation between variables in a study. If the data shows that the correlation of each indicator construct has a greater value than the value of other constructs, then the variable has a high cross-loading factor. The following are the results of cross-loading factors using SmartPLS:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity (Cross Loading Factor) Results

Indicator	SEO (X ₁)	SMMA _s (X ₂)	Brand Awareness (Z)	Brand Equity (Y ₁)	Brand Loyalty (Y ₂)
BrAw01	0,521	0,720	0,881	0,480	0,459
BrAw02	0,566	0,739	0,922	0,459	0,500
BrAw03	0,490	0,643	0,890	0,513	0,547
BrEq01	0,426	0,469	0,425	0,734	0,389
BrEq02	0,632	0,536	0,503	0,929	0,599
BrEq03	0,627	0,496	0,388	0,785	0,699
BrLo01	0,515	0,458	0,465	0,598	0,860
BrLo02	0,593	0,432	0,485	0,677	0,866
BrLo03	0,480	0,396	0,449	0,419	0,774
SEO01	0,869	0,523	0,534	0,659	0,628
SEO02	0,839	0,546	0,462	0,548	0,408
SEO03	0,839	0,484	0,526	0,556	0,625
SEO04	0,582	0,343	0,278	0,355	0,261
SMMA01	0,720	0,605	0,517	0,574	0,543
SMMA02	0,259	0,600	0,345	0,304	0,225
SMMA03	0,490	0,817	0,639	0,478	0,446
SMMA04	0,349	0,744	0,605	0,372	0,317
SMMA05	0,450	0,789	0,622	0,488	0,405
SMMA06	0,269	0,677	0,460	0,315	0,213
SMMA07	0,419	0,744	0,597	0,417	0,296
SMMA08	0,376	0,529	0,420	0,316	0,370
SMMA09	0,449	0,800	0,638	0,557	0,445
SMMA10	0,505	0,777	0,625	0,476	0,374

Based on Table 4.8, it can be concluded that all constructs in the estimated model have met the criteria for discriminant validity. The requirement is that the square root value of the AVE of each construct is greater than the correlation value between constructs, so it can be said that the indicators used in this study have met the requirements. According to Sugiyono (2017:130), reliability testing is how far a measurement result can produce the same data. In Partial Least Square (PLS), reliability testing can use two methods, namely Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha. The following are the results of reliability testing using SmartPLS software.

Table 3. Result of Reliability Testing

Variable	Composite Reliability	Critical Value	Cronbach Alpha	Critical Value	Model Evaluation
.Search Engine Optimization (SEO) (X ₁)	0,839	> 0,7	0,797	> 0,6	Realible
Social Media Marketing Activities (SMMAAs) (X ₂)	0,903.		0,891		Realible
.Brand Awareness (Z)	0,926		0,879		Reliable
Brand Equity (Y ₁)	0,773		0,750		Realible
Brand Loyalty (Y ₂)	0,783		0,780		Reliable

Based on Table 3, the Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha values for each variable are more than 0.7 and 0.6, respectively. So it can be said that the data has high reliability.

B. Structural (Inner) Model

Measurement of the structural model (inner model) aims to test the influence of other latent variables. In PLS, the accuracy of the proposed model can be measured using R-Square (R²) and path coefficient. The structural model test (inner model) is carried out by observing the R² value on the endogenous latent construct and the t-value on each exogenous latent variable against the endogenous latent construct from the bootstrapping results.

According to Indrawati (2017), the R-Square value is the coefficient of determination on the endogenous construct. The R-Square value is the coefficient of determination on the endogenous construct. The higher the R-Square value, the better the prediction model of the proposed research model.

Table 4. R-Square Values

Variable	R-Square
Brand Awareness (Z)	0,629
Brand Equity (Y ₁)	0,291
Brand Loyalty(Y ₂)	0,313

Based on Table 4, it can be seen that the R-Square value for the Brand Awareness (Z) variable is 0.629, the Brand Equity (Y₁) variable is 0.291, and for the Brand Loyalty (Y₂) variable is 0.313. The R-Square value for the Brand Awareness (Z) variable is 62.9%, which means that the Brand Awareness (Z) variable can be explained by the Search Engine Optimization

(X1) variable and the remaining 37.1% is influenced by the Social Media Marketing Activities (X2) variable. The R-Square value for the Brand Equity (Y1) variable is 29.1%, which means that the Brand Equity (Y1) variable can be explained by Search Engine Optimization (X1) and Brand Awareness (Z) and as much as 70.9% is influenced by the Social Media Marketing Activities (X2) variable. Meanwhile, the R-Square value on the Brand Loyalty variable (Y2) is 31.3%, which means that the Brand Loyalty variable (Y2) can be explained by Search Engine Optimization (X1) and Brand Awareness (Z) and the remaining 68.7% is influenced by the Social Media Marketing Activities variable (X2).

Q Square is used to measure how good the observation value is produced by the model and parameter estimates. If the Q Square value is less than 0 (zero), then the model has less predictive relevance, while if the Q Square value is greater than 0 (zero), then the model has a predictive relevance value. The following is the calculation of the inner model test with (predictive relevance) using the formula:

$$Q^2 = \sqrt{1 - (1 - R_1^2)(1 - R_2^2)(1 - R_3^2) \dots (1 - R_p^2)}$$

$$Q^2 = \sqrt{1 - (1 - 0,580^2)(1 - 0,246^2)(1 - 0,246^2)}$$

$$Q^2 = 0,708$$

Predictive Relevance of 0.708 means greater than 0 (zero) explaining that the model has a relevant predictive value. According to Sugiyono (2019:219-220) Hypothesis is a temporary answer to the formulation of research problems. The truth of the hypothesis must be proven through the collected data. The definition of the hypothesis is for the research hypothesis. While statistically, a hypothesis is defined as a statement regarding the state of the population (parameter) whose truth will be tested based on data obtained from the research sample (statistics). In conducting hypothesis testing, the t-statistic value (to) must be compared with the t-table value (tα) with the following hypothesis acceptance provisions:

- 1) If the value of to > (tα), then H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted
- 2) If the value of to < (tα), then H0 is accepted and H1 is rejected.

Table 5. Path Coefficiencie

Variable	Original Sample (O)	Mean Sample (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Search Engine Optimization (X1) to Brand Awareness (Z)	0,178	0,186	0,062	2,863	0,004
Social Media Marketing Activities (X2) to Brand Awareness (Z)	0,673	0,679	0,064	10,496	0,000
Brand Awareness (Z) to Brand Equity (Y1)	0,539	0,553	0,077	7,044	0,000
Brand Awareness (Z) to Brand Loyalty (Y2)	0,559	0,565	0,082	6,783	0,000

In the Search Engine Optimization variable (X1) has a Tcount value that is greater than the table value (2.863 > 1.96) and a significance value that is smaller than the level of accuracy (0.004 < 0.05), then H0 is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that partially there is a significant influence of Search Engine Optimization (X1) on Brand Awareness (Z). The magnitude of the influence of X1 on Z is 2.863. This shows that Brand Awareness is influenced by Search Engine Optimization on the Pikiran-Rakyat.com site. While in the Social Media Marketing Activities variable. has a Tcount value that is greater than the table value (10.496 > 1.96) and a significance value that is smaller than the level of accuracy (0.000 < 0.05), then H0 is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that partially there is a significant influence of Social Media Marketing Activities (X2)

on Brand Awareness (Z). The magnitude of the influence of X2 on Z is 10.496. This shows that Brand Awareness is influenced by Social Media Marketing Activities on the Pikiran-Rakyat.com site. In the Brand Awareness variable, it has a Tcount value that is greater than the table value ($7.004 > 1.96$) and a significance value that is smaller than the level of accuracy ($0.000 < 0.05$), then H_0 is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that partially there is a significant influence of Brand Awareness (Z) on Brand Equity (Y1). The magnitude of the influence of Z on Y1 is 7.004, this shows that Brand Awareness is influenced by Brand Equity on the Pikiran-Rakyat.com site. However, the Brand Awareness variable also has a Tcount value that is greater than the table ($6.783 > 1.96$) and has a significance value that is smaller than the level of accuracy ($0.000 < 0.005$), then H_0 is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that partially there is a significant influence of Brand Awareness (Z) on Brand Loyalty (Y2). The magnitude of the influence of Z on Y2 is 6.783, this shows that Brand Awareness is influenced by Brand Loyalty on the Pikiran-Rakyat.com site.

CONCLUSION

Based on the Research Results and Discussion on THE EFFECT OF DIGITAL MARKETING THROUGH SEO AND SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ACTIVITIES ON BRAND AWARENESS IN BUILDING BRAND EQUITY AND BRAND LOYALTY OF THE PIKIRAN-RAKYAT.COM SITE that have been presented in the previous chapter, several conclusions can be drawn that the Researcher hopes will be able to provide answers to the problems formulated in this Research. The following are the conclusions and suggestions based on the results of research on the influence of digital marketing through SEO and social media marketing activities on brand awareness, brand equity, and brand loyalty of the Pikiran-Rakyat.com site:

1. Search Engine Optimization (X1): Overall, statements about SEO are included in the good category, but there are still statements with the lowest scores related to the frequency of news searches based on current topics. This indicates that users may not often search for the latest information.
2. Social Media Marketing Activities (X2): Although in the fairly good category, there are statements regarding content provided through social media that get the lowest score, indicating that the benefits of the content need to be improved.
3. Brand Awareness (Z): The results show that overall brand awareness is good, but there are statements regarding user memory of the characteristics of the news portal that need to be strengthened.
4. Brand Equity (Y1): The brand equity value among respondents is also in the good category, but there are aspects that must be considered in order to increase to the very good category.
5. Brand Loyalty (Y2): Brand loyalty measurements also show positive results, but there is room for further improvement so that users are more attached to the brand.

RECOMENDATION

1. SEO Improvement: Pikiran Rakyat Media Network is advised to increase the frequency and relevance of the latest information so that users are more often involved in searching for trending news.
2. Social Media Content: Can provide more useful and interesting information on social media to increase respondents' perceptions of the benefits of the content provided.
3. Strengthening Brand Awareness: Marketing strategies that focus more on introducing the unique characteristics of news portals can help users remember the brand more.
4. Brand Equity Development: Companies are advised to consider offering more attractive content than competitors by providing more value to the news presented.
5. Recommendation Strategy: Encourage the use of social media to share news content and recommend the portal to others, this will help increase loyalty and brand awareness.

With these steps, Pikiran Rakyat Media Network is expected to improve their position in the market and increase user engagement and satisfaction.

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